

Conductance of Sodium Sulphate in Dioxane-water Mixtures at 35°

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The conductances of sodium sulphate solutions in 10, 20, and 30% of dioxane-water mixtures have been measured at 35°. This study has been undertaken with a view to ascertaining the effect of the solvent composition on the diameter of the ion pair NaSO_4^- .

Sodium sulphate used was of G. R. E. Merck variety. The SO_4^{2-} content was analysed by the standard method. The preparation of the solvent and solution and conductance measurements have been described previously¹.

The plot of the equivalent conductance against the square root of the concentration was not linear. Hence the method of Bevan and Monk² was adopted for evaluating the value of Λ_0 , i.e., by plotting $\Lambda + b\sqrt{C}$ against C , where 'b' is the calculated coefficient of Onsager's conductivity expression. The dissociation constants of the ion pair NaSO_4^- at 10, 20, and 30% solvent composition (wt % of dioxane) have been calculated by the method of Jenkin and Monk^{3,4} and diameters of the ion pairs from Bjerrum's equation⁵. These values are recorded in Table I. The distance of the closest approach has not been calculated by the Stokes method as the product $\Lambda_{0.70}$ is not constant (as can be seen from Table I). The values of the diameter of the ion pair NaSO_4^- , however, indicate that solvation sphere of the ion is affected.

TABLE I

Solvent composition (wt. % of dioxane).	Λ_0 .	$\Lambda_{0.70}$.	$K \times 10^2$.	Diameters of the ion pair.
10	174.50 ohm^{-1}	1.5036	5.43	0.3894 Å
20	150.50	1.5862	2.67	0.6137
20	118.00	1.3875	1.97	0.6462

The authors are thankful to Dr. D. Patnaik, Professor of Chemistry, for guidance.

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Received October 10, 1964.

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